

Analyze The Weakness Of The 2023 Reformed Curriculum To The Education System: A Case Study Of Four (4) Selected Secondary Schools In Mbala District Of Northern Province In Zambia.

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Abstract- At the time of independence from Britain in 1964, the educational system in Zambia was racially segregated and heavily biased against Africans. However, since Zambia got independence, its education system has seen great change. With the coming in of the 2023 reformed educational curriculum our education system will be equal to that of the western world although it will take a lot of time to reach their level. This is because there are some hiccups in the implementation of our reformed curriculum. This paper briefly reviews the weakness of the 2023 reformed curriculum to the education system: a case study of Four (4) selected Secondary Schools in Mbala District of Northern Province in Zambia. The research has discussed successes and failures in program implementation as evidenced by challenges faced by various institutions within the ministry of education. Other factors contributing to problems with the successful implementation of educational policies have been a poor economy, inadequate supply of teachers above the primary level, problems with curriculum relevance, and an entrenched debate about the merits of English language versus native language teaching.

Keywords - In relation to the weaknesses of the 2023 Zambia's reformed competence-based curriculum to the education system here are summarizing definitions for some of the terms used in this report:

1. Education
2. Reform
3. Curriculum
4. Institution
5. Weakness
6. Implementation
7. Competence
8. Infrastructure
9. Secondary school
10. Confidentiality

I. Introduction

Early 2025 Zambia's curriculum development centre revised and circulated an educational curriculum for implementation and use in Zambian schools. This curriculum was revised in 2023, in readiness for 2025 implementation. This curriculum implementation took steps that were unclear and had to be changed from time to time but still looks like an old curriculum despite having good and progressive contents. This is the reason why this research is going to analyse its weaknesses. The Objectives of this study are review why and when the Zambian educational curriculum is revised in Zambia, Assess the Zambian curriculum review procedure in Zambia and to discuss the barriers to a successful implementation of the 2023 Zambian educational curriculum by

most Zambian schools. The research will also help explain the challenges of the 2023 Zambia's reformed curriculum to the education system as well as provide solutions needed for the successful implementation of the 2023 Zambia's reformed educational curriculum. Hence, simulating people's interest in the educational system of Zambia by donating various items to various institutions within their reach to facilitate the smooth implementation of the 2023 Zambia's reformed educational curriculum for the benefit of the learner.

II. Literature Review

Zambia's educational system has undergone significant changes before the current 2023 education reform. Basically, there have been three significant education policies in Zambia since independence. These policies include the 1977 Educational Reform, the 1992 Focus on Learning, and the 1996 Educating Our Future. These policies have shaped the Zambian education system by emphasizing different aspects of development and access to education aimed at improving access, quality and equity.

1. Educational Reform (1977).
2. Education for All (1990).
3. Focus on Learning (1992).
4. . Educating Our Future (1996).
5. Free Education Policy (2022).

Curriculum Reforms particularly the recent reforms including the 2023 education reform focus on making the curriculum more relevant to the contemporary Zambian context, emphasizing critical thinking, problem-solving, and practical skills.

Zambia's education system has made significant strides over the years, but it still faces several challenges that encumber its ability to provide quality education for all. <https://youthvillagezm.com/2024/10>, presents top five challenges presently impacting Zambia's education system.

1. Access to Quality Education.
2. Teacher Shortages and Training.
3. Infrastructure Deficiencies.
4. Quality of Curriculum and Relevance.
5. Funding and Resource Allocation.

III. Research Methodology

3.1 Research design

In order to Analyze the weaknesses of the 2023 reformed curriculum to the education system. It is necessary to develop a data collection that would cover at least four secondary schools, four primary schools and two community primary schools in Mbala district of Northern Province in Zambia. It is from here that the researcher would be able to Analyse the weaknesses of the 2023 reformed curriculum to the education system. Qualitative data from interviews with education officials at the district

education board secretary's office will enable the researcher to analysis data received in the questionnaire.

3.2 Participants

Employing the qualitative methodology will enable an in-depth analysis the weaknesses of the 2023 reformed curriculum to the education system: a case study of Four (4) selected Secondary Schools in Mbala District of Northern Province in Zambia. The qualitative data that will be used will be survey method which involves eight (8) school administrators, sixty (60) teachers and three (3) officers at the district education board secretary's office. The questionnaires are designed to analyse the weaknesses of the 2023 reformed curriculum to the education system: a case study of Four (4) selected Secondary Schools in Mbala District of Northern Province in Zambia.

3.3 Instruments

Questionnaires comprising of both closed ended and open-ended questions will be used as instruments for data collections. Closed ended questions facilitate coding of questions for easy data processing, cost effective and it also provide quantitative data which will be used for analysis.

3.4 Procedure

The research method will involve a survey in which the data will be collected from pre-defined group of respondents to gain information and insight on the analysis the weaknesses of the 2023 reformed curriculum to the education system: a case study of Four (4) selected Secondary Schools in Mbala District of Northern Province in Zambia. The procedure will be as follows:

Firstly, the research will identify four secondary schools from sample of four zones of Mbala district.

Secondly the researcher will decide the type of survey to be used, there after design the survey questionnaires, and then move round the four secondary schools in the selected four to distribute questionnaires for respondents to provide answers.

Thirdly, the questionnaires will then be collected with respondents' responses for analyse of the survey results.

Lastly, the researcher will write up the survey results using comparative analysis in which a lot of data is relatively collected at short space of time to ensure cost effective and takes less time for respondents to complete. However, some responses may not be specific, questionnaires may be misinterpreted and the research may not get a full story for those limitations, face to face interview will also be used to discuss various issues on the 2023 reformed curriculum to the education system.

3.5 Data Collection

During the study a cross sectional survey approach will be used as the appropriate method to the study. The research methods will involve the use of questionnaires as well as interviews to consolidate the findings of the study.

Primary data collection and secondary data will be used by means of questionnaire and interview (primary). Field visit to the selected schools will also be done with the guidance of the district education board secretary's introduction to school administrators in the selected schools in the district.

3.6 Data Analysis

Data collected using questionnaires will be checked for consistency, uniformity and accuracy and then will be examined and analysed to find out if the objectives of the research has been achieved compared to the findings. In order to the meet the research's objectives this analysis will also find out which measures and activities officials at the district education board secretary's office and school administration have put in place in order to strengthen the 2023 reformed curriculum to the education system in Mbala district of northern province Zambia.

IV. Findings

1. **Inadequate Teacher Training:** Many teachers lack the necessary training to effectively implement the Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) methodology.
2. **Resource Constraints:** Schools face shortages of teaching materials, infrastructure, and technology, hindering smooth implementation.
3. **Infrastructure Deficiencies:** Rural schools struggle with inadequate classrooms, libraries, and sanitation facilities.
4. **Funding Limitations:** Insufficient funding affects teacher salaries, learning materials, and infrastructure development.
5. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Limited involvement of teachers, parents, and communities in curriculum development and implementation.

When reflecting on these findings, this report reminds us that curriculum reform is a complex and an ongoing process, that requires concerted efforts from government, educators, and communities to ensure that Zambia's education system prepares learners for future opportunities.

V. Discussions Of Findings

Below are some of other weakness of the Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) in Zambia brought out by the participants during the research.

Many teachers aren't adequately trained or prepared to implement the CBC, leading to ineffective teaching methods coupled with limited Resources, Schools lack sufficient textbooks, syllabi, and modules, hindering the smooth implementation of the curriculum.

Another major challenge of the 2023 reformed educational curriculum is lack of Infrastructure resulting in inadequate classrooms, laboratories, and computer facilities hinder practical learning. This is brought about insufficient Funding in most secondary school, affecting the provision of teaching and learning materials, infrastructure, and teacher training.

Major stakeholders such as teachers, parents, and communities are often not adequately involved in curriculum development and implementation thereby lacking a clear understanding of the Competence Based Curriculum pathways and implementation strategies

Lastly but not the least, Assessment Challenges is another weakness of the Competence-Based Curriculum (CBC) in Zambia's 2023 reformed educational curriculum as School-based assessments and national exams pose challenges due to inadequate training and resources.

VI. Conclusion

Since the 2023 reformed educational Competence Based Curriculum was introduced early 2025, teachers, parents and administrators across the country are already reporting, Shortage of teacher training in Competence Based Curriculum methodology, lack of adequate teaching and learning materials, Confusion in assessment methods, Rural schools falling behind due to large class sizes, lack of resources, limited technology equipment in schools among others. These challenges are exactly the same concerns that have been documented in several countries that implemented Competence Based Curriculum (CBC) before us. They reflect a predictable pattern when CBC is introduced without sufficient preparation. With these evidences It is important to emphasize that competence-based curriculum in Zambia be revised heavily or better reverted back to blended approaches because, Competencies are difficult to measure consistently, teachers are overwhelmed without proper training above all curriculum content is too broad.

VII. Recommendations

1. Postpone or suspend full-scale CBC implementation until adequate preparedness is achieved.
2. Conduct a national audit of teacher training, infrastructure, funding, and resources.
3. Engage stakeholders in curriculum development and implementation.
4. Develop a phased, well-funded implementation roadmap prioritizing equity and learner progress.
5. Advocate for increased investment in teacher training, infrastructure, and resources.
6. Support ongoing monitoring and evaluation of the curriculum implementation.

References

1. Banathy, B. H. (2000), Guided evolution of society. A system view. Kluwer, New York.
2. Bertalanffy, V. L. (1968), Systems Theory, University of Alberta Edmonton. Canada.
3. <https://accessjournal.nkrumah.edu.zm/index.php/knuj/article/view/27>.
4. <https://generisonline.com/an-overview-of-the-education-system-in-zambia/>.
5. https://www.academia.edu/24458763/Education_system_in_Zambia.

6. <https://www.researchgate.net>.
7. <https://youthvillagezm.com/2024/10>.
8. Rodgers, E. M. (2003), Diffusion of Innovations, Macmillan Publishing Co. Canada.